

PREDICTION OF FIBRE ORIENTATION IN SHORT GLASS FIBRE REINFORCED COMPOSITE INJECTION MOULDING

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1 General Introduction

For many years thermoplastics have been extensively used in a wide variety of applications due to their relatively cheap cost and high processability, particularly by injection moulding. However, commodity polymers such as polypropylene and Nylon have relatively poor mechanical properties, which limits their use to non-structural applications. The use of short glass fibre reinforcement is a well established means of significantly improving mechanical performance without compromising processability. Apart from the fibre and matrix properties, the mechanical properties of the final component are crucially dependent on the fibre orientation distribution developed during the process. The most important variable, arguably, is the fibre orientation distribution produced in a component during the injection moulding process, which depends on a number of factors, most notably the mould cavity shape. Consequently, accurate prediction of fibre orientation is essential for the design process of commercial components [1].

Within this paper we compare predictions of short glass fibre orientation developed during injection moulding based on the reduced strain closure (RSC) [2], Moldflow Adjusted Folgar-Tucker and the original Folgar-Tucker [3] models within Autodesk Simulation Moldflow 2013. Test geometries include simple flat plates of 2 and 4 mm thicknesses (2 mm data will only be shown here) and a centre-gated disc of 1 and 2 mm thickness. Accuracy of fibre orientation predictions from both models have been evaluated by comparing with experimental data at specific locations within the test mouldings.

2 Sample Preparation and Testing

2.1 Injection Moulding

A series of geometries were moulded at the University of Bradford to provide samples for fibre orientation measurement at the University of Leeds. Two flat plates 40 mm wide and 120 mm long were selected with thicknesses of 2 and 4 mm. Both plates were gated at one end using a fan and well configuration, the 2 mm plate having an inlet gate thickness of 0.5 mm and the 4 mm plate having a gate inlet thickness of 2mm, Figure 1. An additional pair of centre-gated discs were also moulded with diameter 95 mm and thicknesses of 1 and 2 mm, Figure 2. All samples were moulded from Rhodia 216 v40 a 40% wt short glass fibre reinforced Nylon 6.

2.2 Fibre Orientation Measurement

Fibre orientation measurements were conducted at the University of Leeds using an optical microscopy technique [4]. Samples were taken at two locations (A and B) along the flow path within the flat plate geometries, Figure 1. Orientation angles θ and ϕ were averaged over the sample width to produce orientation distribution plots through the plate thickness. The centre-gated disc geometry had three sample locations (A, B and C) located 16.5, 25.15 and 36.3 mm from the centre. Samples were also taken at four radial locations around the disc at 90° angles. Orientation angles θ and ϕ were compared to ensure accurate results and suitable mould balancing. These results will not be shown here.

3 Injection Moulding Analysis

Autodesk Simulation Moldflow fibre orientation predictions for short glass fibre reinforced materials re implemented using the three available models;

Folgar-Tucker, modified Folgar-Tucker and Reduced Strain Closure, with specification of each model parameter c_i , D_z and k defined so as to obtain the optimum analysis result.

A review of each of these models was presented by Wang et al (2010) [5], where each model was related to the second order orientation tensor (Advani and Tucker, 1987), defined as

$$A = \langle pp \rangle \quad (1)$$

where p is the unit vector along the fibre length and “ $\langle \rangle$ ” denotes a volumetric average domain.

The Folgar-Tucker model defines the orientation tensor in terms of vorticity (W), rate of deformation tensor (D), a particle shape parameter ζ and the fibre interaction coefficient c_i .

$$\frac{DA}{Dt} = (W \cdot A - A \cdot W) + \zeta(D \cdot A + A \cdot D - 2\Lambda : D) + 2C_i \dot{\gamma}(I - 3A) \quad (2)$$

Λ is the fourth order orientation tensor and is commonly approximated by a closure function.

The modified version of the Folgar-Tucker model, developed by Moldflow, includes an additional parameter D_z , ranging between 0 and 1, and seeks to reduce the effect of the fibre interaction term. A D_z value of 1 returns the modified equation to the original Folgar-Tucker model.

$$\frac{DA}{Dt} = (W \cdot A - A \cdot W) + \zeta(D \cdot A + A \cdot D - 2\Lambda : D) + 2C_i \dot{\gamma}(I - (2 + D_z)A) \quad (3)$$

The Reduced Strain Closure model modifies the Folgar-Tucker equation (2) by introducing an additional scalar factor k to slow the fibre orientation kinetics. Currently k can only be assigned from experimental data.

$$\frac{DA}{Dt} = (W \cdot A - A \cdot W) + \zeta(D \cdot A + A \cdot D - 2[\Lambda + (1 - \kappa)(L - M:\Lambda)]:D) + 2\kappa C_i \dot{\gamma}(I - 3A). \quad (4)$$

Table 1 summarises the feasible applications of the three fibre orientation models in terms of Autodesk Moldflow analyses along side the associated limits of their respective parameters.

Midplane / Dual Domain	3D
Folgar-Tucker Fibre interaction coefficient c_i (<0.1) Larger c_i implies more fibre-fibre interaction	Folgar-Tucker (Default) Fibre interaction coefficient c_i (<0.1) Larger c_i implies more fibre-fibre interaction
Modified Folgar-Tucker (Default) Thickness moment of interaction D_z ($0 < D_z < 1$) Fibre interaction coefficient c_i (<0.1)	-
Reduced Strain Closure (RSC) Scalar factor k (<1) k determined by fitting experimental data Fibre interaction coefficient c_i (<0.1)	Reduced Strain Closure (RSC) Scalar factor k (<1) k determined by fitting experimental data Fibre interaction coefficient c_i (<0.1)

Table 1. Fibre orientation models within Autodesk Moldflow including limits of their respective parameters

All geometries were modeled as midplane analyses with 20 layers through the thickness. In order to aid comparisons between experimental and computational fibre orientation data a line of coincident nodes were placed along the fibre orientation measurement locations. As an example, the flat plate geometry contained 2000 elements each with 20 layers through thickness. Alternate mesh densities were also studied and found to produce similar predictions of fibre orientation.

Fibre orientation model parameters were defined as shown within Table 2, with modified Folgar-Tucker D_z values decreasing from 0.8 to 0.2 in 0.2 steps.

Fibre Orientation Model	c_i	D_z	k
Folgar-Tucker	0.1	-	-
Folgar-Tucker	0.01	-	-
Folgar-Tucker	0.001	-	-
Folgar-Tucker	0.0001	-	-
Folgar-Tucker	0.00001	-	-
Modified	0.1	0.8	-
Folgar-Tucker			
Modified	0.01	0.8	-
Folgar-Tucker			
Modified	0.001	0.8	-
Folgar-Tucker			
Modified	0.0001	0.8	-
Folgar-Tucker			
Modified	0.00001	0.8	-
Folgar-Tucker			
Modified	0.1	0.6	-
Folgar-Tucker			
...	-
Modified	0.00001	0.2	-
Folgar-Tucker			
RSC	0.00001	-	0.8
RSC	0.00001	-	0.6
RSC	0.00001	-	0.4
RSC	0.00001	-	0.2
RSC	0.00001	-	0.1
RSC	0.00001	-	0.01
RSC	0.00001	-	0.001
RSC	0.00001	-	0.0001
RSC	0.00001	-	0.00001

Table 2. Fibre orientation model parameters

Based on preliminary results from the orientation parameters shown in Table 2, optimum values of each parameter were specified for the 4 geometries based on comparison with experimental values of fibre orientation.

4 Results

4.1 Experimental Fibre Orientation Data

Fibre orientation measurements for the 2 mm flat plate geometry are shown in Figure 3, with typical skin – shell – core type structures. The orientation of the core region at location A (0.46) relates to a slight transverse fibre orientation compared to the direction of flow. As the flow extends to location B the fibres are almost completely aligned with the direction of flow, the minimum orientation factor being 0.65. As a note, a fibre orientation factor of 1.0 would denote fibres perfectly aligned in the direction of flow (X).

For the centre-gated geometry, experimental fibre orientation data demonstrates an asymmetric skin – shell – core structure with the core tending towards the top of the sample nearest to the point of injection, Figure 4. Also, due to the radial flow nature of the geometry, the orientation along the flow path results in fibres transverse to the direction of flow, ie converse to the flat plate geometry.

4.2 Predictions of Fibre Orientation

The Folgar-Tucker model tends to over predict the level of fibre orientation within the shell region of the flat plate geometries for all values of fibre interaction coefficient c_i with the exception of 0.1, which resulted in an approximately random orientation distribution though the entire sample thickness, Figure 5. This follows published data on the application of the Folgar-Tucker model for highly filled systems and was the cause for the modification of the theory by AutoDesk Moldflow. However, based on the results shown in Figure 5 the optimum value for the fibre interaction coefficient c_i was determined to be approximately 0.025.

With the inclusion of the thickness moment of interaction parameter D_z the average orientation at location A of the flat plate geometry was shown to change significantly for the modified Folgar-Tucker model, with respect to both fibre interaction coefficient and D_z , Figure 6. Notably reductions in the thickness moment of interaction resulted in corresponding reductions in the average orientation. At fibre interaction coefficients of 0.01 and above, the D_z above 0.4 converged whilst those below 0.4 continued to decrease the orientation average.

Taking the fibre interaction coefficient (c_i) of 0.001 as an example, Figure 7, the reduction in average orientation with respect D_z can be seen to be not a reduction in maximum fibre orientation, in fact for a D_z value of 0.4 the maximum is higher than that for a D_z of 1.0, but a broadening of the fibre orientation distribution curve through the sample thickness. Specifically, for a D_z value of 1.0, relating to the original Folgar-Tucker formulation, the region of high orientation above 0.9 within the shell covers nearly 50% of the sample thickness. Lower values of D_z such as 0.4 and 0.2 showed an initially high degree of orientation in the shell followed by a rapid reduction within the outer 0.5 mm of the sample thickness. The minimum fibre orientation for all modified Folgar-Tucker models was shown in the centre of the sample, having an orientation factor of just below 0.5.

Based on the results shown in Figures 6 and 7, the optimum values for the modified version of the Folgar-Tucker model were determined for both locations of the 2 mm flat plate geometry ($D_z = 0.15$ and $c_i = 0.0057$). Comparison with experimental data is shown in Figure 8.

The Reduced Strain Closure model showed a greater degree of change on the maximum fibre orientation with respect to both the scalar factor k and the fibre interaction coefficient (c_i) compared to the Folgar-Tucker and modified Folgar-Tucker models, Figure 9. At c_i values, below 0.001, the scalar factor k reduced the maximum orientation from 0.96 for $k=1.0$ to 0.9 for k in the range of 0.01 to 0.00001. A c_i of 0.001 showed almost identical maximum orientation for all values of k . Above 0.001 c_i the maximum orientation in the plate geometry reduced significantly with increasing k , with $k>0.4$ having the lowest fibre orientation maximum of 0.5, randomly oriented fibres. When considering the average fibre orientation at location A, a similar behavior as described above was found although the convergent result at the c_i value of 0.001 shifted in the case of the average orientation to approximately 0.01, Figure 10.

Overall, the Reduced Strain Closure model showed the closest approximation to the experimental fibre orientation distribution for the flat plate geometry, with a k value of 0.1 and c_i 0.0057, Figure 11.

5 Discussion

5.1 Comparison with Published Data

Results shown within the previous section defined the optimum values of the three fibre orientation models for the 2 mm flat plate geometry, Table 3.

Fibre Orientation Model	c_i	D_z	k
Folgar-Tucker	0.025	-	-
Modified Folgar-Tucker	0.0057	0.15	-
RSC	0.0057	-	0.1

Table 3. Optimum fibre orientation model parameters based on 2 mm flat plate geometry

When compared to published work, the optimum value of c_i described above (0.025 for the Folgar-Tucker model) was found to be significantly higher than for example 0.00043 as calculated from the proposed theory of Tucker and Advani, equation 5

$$c_i = 0.0184 \exp\left(-0.7148V_f \frac{L}{d}\right) \quad (4)$$

where V_f is the volume fraction of glass fibres within the composite (21%), L is the fibre length (250 μm) and d is the fibre diameter (10 μm). In contrast, the optimum value for both the modified Folgar-Tucker and Reduced Strain Closure models appears closer to the proposed theory although is an order of magnitude higher.

5.2 Comparison with Centre-Gated Disc Analysis

It is of significant scientific and commercial interest to determine if these optimum values for fibre orientation models such as the Folgar-Tucker and Reduced Strain Closure are applicable across different geometries. For this reason a series of analyses were conducted using the optimum values

described above for both 4 mm flat plates and the centre-gated disc. The results for the 2 mm centre-gated disc are discussed below.

The optimum value for the fibre interaction coefficient as described by the 2 mm flat plate geometry analysis (0.025) has been used within the 2 mm centre-gated disc model. Results from this analysis showed significant differences between experimental and predicted fibre orientations, Figure 12. Whilst the analysis correctly predicted a core orientation of approximately 0.2, the width of the core region was significantly under predicted. Orientation within the shell region was also over predicted.

The modified version of the Folgar-Tucker model was in closer agreement to the experimental data at both locations A and C of the centre-gated disc. Significantly, whilst the maximum and minimum orientation in the direction of flow remained almost unchanged, the shape of the orientation distribution curve showed a wider core region. However, as with the flat plate geometry, the model resulted in an overall over prediction of orientation in the direction of flow.

In contrast to the flat plate geometry, the Reduced Strain Closure model showed no improvement in fibre orientation predictions compared to the modified version of the Folgar-Tucker model. In fact, the levels of orientation through the entire thickness of the centre-gated disc were significantly higher than those found experimentally. Specifically the maximum orientation was predicted to be 0.825 compared to 0.73 experiments and the minimum 0.39 compared to 0.073. Also of interest is the lack of change of fibre orientation distribution along the flow path from locations A and C. Further work is currently ongoing to assess the effects of the scalar factor k and fibre interaction coefficient c_i on the centre-gated geometry. Results from this work will be presented at ICCM 19.

4 Conclusions

Based on the results to date it appears that the Reduced Strain Closure fibre orientation prediction model offers a clear route to enhanced fibre

orientation analysis accuracy. It should however be noted that the specification of the scalar factor k is currently only determinable via experimental comparison and as such not viable for complex geometries. Within these studies, whilst the Reduced Strain Closure model provided the most accurate prediction for orientation within the flat plate geometry, it failed to achieve the same degree of agreement when applied to radial flow, within the centre-gated disc. Further work is currently underway to investigate the thickness effects during the moulding an analysis of the 4 mm flat plate and 1 mm centre-gated disc. This work will be presented at ICCM 19.

The modified version of the Folgar-Tucker also demonstrated improved fibre orientation analysis predictions when compared to the original unmodified case. Whilst, this model over predicted the level of orientation in both cases it remains of interest. Work is ongoing to assess the effect of geometry changes such as thickness on the accuracy of this model. It remains the industry standard at the time of writing and the default model within AutoDesk Simulation Moldflow.

Fig.1. End gated flat plate geometry with fibre orientation measurement locations A and B

Fig. 2. Centre-gated disc geometry with fibre orientation measurement locations A, B and C

Fig. 3. Fibre orientation measurements for 2 mm thickness flat plate geometry at Locations A and B

Fig. 4. Fibre orientation measurements for 2 mm centre-gated disc at Locations A, B and C

Fig. 5. Fibre orientation predictions for the Folgar-Tucker model with varying c_1

Fig. 6. The effect of fibre interaction coefficient and thickness moment of interaction for the modified version of the Folgar-Tucker model on the average fibre orientation at location A of the flat plate

Fig. 7. Thickness moment of interaction (D_z) effect on fibre orientation distribution through the sample thickness of 2 mm flat plate at location A

Fig. 8. Optimum modified Folgar-Tucker model fibre orientation predictions for locations A and B of the 2 mm flat plate

Fig. 9. The effect of fibre interaction coefficient (c_i) and scalar factor (k) for the Reduced Strain Closure model on the maximum fibre orientation in the direction of flow at Location A for the 2 mm flat plate

Fig. 10. The effect of fibre interaction coefficient (c_i) and scalar factor (k) for the Reduced Strain Closure model on the average fibre orientation in the direction of flow at location A for the 2 mm flat plate

Fig. 11. Optimum Reduced Strain Closure model fibre orientation prediction at location A for the 2 mm flat plate

Fig. 12. Folgar-Tucker fibre orientation predictions for locations A and C of the centre-gated disc using optimum c_i from flat plate analysis

Fig. 13. Modified Folgar-Tucker fibre orientation predictions for locations A and C of the centre-gated disc using optimum c_i and D_z from flat plate analysis

Fig. 14. Reduced Strain Closure fibre orientation predictions for locations A and C of the centre-gated disc using optimum c_i and D_z from flat plate analysis

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